

Title: Website optimization for a European project: Analysis of websites of European Erasmus+ projects with good practice badge linked to the KA220 Higher Education category

Authors: Alba Rozas Fueyo and Juan José Boté-Vericad

Author's Affiliation: Facultat d'Informació i Mitjans Audiovisuals. Universitat de Barcelona

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STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of the Contribution

This study aims to examine and assess the quality and effectiveness of websites developed by European Erasmus+ projects that have been awarded a "good practice" badge under the KA220 Higher Education (KA220-HED) category. The central objective is to derive actionable insights and strategic recommendations for the optimisation of the website of the GEDIS project, a European Erasmus+ initiative dedicated to promoting gender diversity and equality within the field of Library and Information Science (LIS). Through this analysis, the study seeks to identify which web design elements, communication strategies, and content structures are most conducive to being recognised as a good practice by national Erasmus+ agencies, with the intention of applying these lessons to enhance the online presence and outreach effectiveness of GEDIS. Projects awarded the good practice badge are recognised by national Erasmus+ agencies. This badge demonstrates excellence in project implementation, innovation, and dissemination. This distinction serves as a practical proxy for quality. It offers a credible benchmark for identifying successful digital communication strategies applicable to GEDIS project and potentially transferable to other projects.

Value of the Contribution

This research provides a novel contribution to the field of digital communication and project dissemination within the context of European educational initiatives. Specifically, it offers a structured, practical, and replicable methodology for assessing the quality of Erasmus+ project websites. By evaluating web quality across multiple dimensions—such as branding, multilingual

accessibility, use of Creative Commons licensing, visual coherence, and communication efficiency—the study not only informs the optimisation of the GEDIS website but also establishes generalisable principles that can be adopted by other KA220-HED projects. Moreover, this research incorporates a gender-sensitive perspective, aligning with the thematic focus of GEDIS, and demonstrating how gender considerations can be integrated into digital dissemination practices. Although the study focuses on Erasmus+ KA220-HED projects specifically. The findings may apply to academic or institutional project websites. The indicators employed—such as multilingual accessibility, consistent branding, and clarity of content—are broadly applicable across educational and research dissemination platforms.

Research Outline

The research focuses on a sample of 32 Erasmus+ projects selected from Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain, and Croatia—countries represented in the GEDIS consortium. These projects were all completed between 2020 and 2021 and have been recognised with a good practice badge by their respective national agencies. Bosnia and Herzegovina, although part of the GEDIS consortium, was excluded from the sample due to its ineligibility to participate in this KA220 category until the 2024 Erasmus+ call.

Data for the analysis were primarily collected from the European Commission's Erasmus+ project results platform, which provides access to official websites and published outputs of funded projects. The evaluation was conducted using a heuristic framework based on established literature on web usability and quality indicators. Specifically, it draws upon methodologies by Codina (2006; 2008), Petrie & Benvan (2009), Petrie et al., (2015), Morales-Vargas (2021), and Pedraza-Jiménez et al. (2016), which were adapted to reflect the context of Erasmus+ digital dissemination. The analysis is structured around four principal parameters: (1) Structure and Navigation; (2) Visual Identity and Branding; (3) Content Quality; and (4) Communication and Dissemination. Within these categories, 27 specific indicators were applied, including aspects such as clarity of navigation menus, consistency of visual design, accessibility of multilingual content, and presence of gender-relevant information.

The research remains in progress; however, preliminary findings suggest the emergence of recurrent design and content strategies among high-performing websites. The study adopts a gender-sensitive lens to examine websites. It focuses on inclusive language, visual representation, and content accessibility (Lin & Hsieh, 2016; Rode, 2011). These elements help

reflect a broader commitment to gender diversity. Not all project websites explicitly address gender in their design. This lens is applied as a qualitative layer in analysis. It is included under the communication and dissemination evaluation category. The approach aligns with the core objectives of the GEDIS project. These strategies include clear and intuitive site navigation, consistent use of project branding, effective multilingual support, proper licensing of educational materials, and proactive dissemination of project outcomes through diverse media. Such practices are now being considered for implementation in the GEDIS project website to ensure both compliance with good practice standards and enhanced user engagement.

REFERENCES

Codina, L. (2006). *Evaluación de calidad en sitios web: Metodología de proyectos de análisis sectoriales y de realización de auditorías* (v. 2008) [Documento reprografiado]. Universitat Pompeu Fabra. Área de Biblioteconomía y Documentación, Departamento de Periodismo y de Comunicación Audiovisual. <https://www.lluiscodina.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/procedimientos2008.pdf>

Codina, L. (2008). *Metodología de análisis y evaluación de recursos digitales en línea* (v. 7, Segona part) [Documento reprografiado]. Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Sección Ciencias de la Documentación. https://www.lluiscodina.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/indicadores_2008.pdf

Lin, C. J., & Hsieh, T.-L. (2016). Exploring the design criteria of website interfaces for gender. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 53, 306-311.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ergon.2016.02.002>

Morales-Vargas, A. (2021). *Evaluación de calidad en sitios web: Factores de análisis, métodos y propuesta de un modelo para el desarrollo de nuevos instrumentos* [Tesis doctoral, Universitat Pompeu Fabra]. TDX. <https://www.tdx.cat/handle/10803/673029>

Pedraza-Jiménez, R., Codina Bonilla, L., & Guallar Delgado, J. (2016). *Calidad en sitios web: Método de análisis general, e-commerce, imágenes, hemerotecas y turismo*. Editorial UOC.

Petrie, H., & Bevan, N. (2009). *The evaluation of accessibility, usability and user experience*. <http://www.crcpress.com/product/isbn/9780805862805>

Petrie, H., Savva, A., & Power, C. D. (2015). Towards a unified definition of web accessibility. In *Proceedings of the 12th Web for All Conference* (p. 35). ACM.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/2745555.2746650>

Rode, J. A. (2011). A theoretical agenda for feminist HCI. *Interacting with Computers*, 23(5), 393–400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intcom.2011.04.005>